

ABOUT LINGUISTIC UNITS IN BILINGUAL SPEECH

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Abstract:

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About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

One of the interesting and relevant issues for linguistics related to the problem of "language and society" seems to us the question of bilingualism, and where, like nowhere else, the influence of social conditions on the development of the language is manifested. It is here, in bilingualism that the linguistic and sociological approaches to language learning organically merge into one inseparable whole - into a kind of dual unity. And this dual unity is strictly necessary here, because bilingualism, or bilingualism, is a linguistic object in its material and an object of sociology for internal reasons for the emergence and functioning in society. In other words, the linguistic and sociological moments in bilingualism are closely connected and interdependent, but at the same time it is indisputable that social, specifically historical reasons always lie at the heart of bilingualism. There is no need to prove that the study of specific forms and types of bilingualism has political, linguo-theoretical and practical significance for us. Bilingualism or multilingualism is a very common phenomenon.

Bilingualism, arising from the practical need for communication of speakers of different languages in the same production team or place of residence, is becoming a progressive factor in the rapprochement of multilingual peoples. Naturally, because the scientific understanding of bilingualism is not only theoretical, but also of great practical importance. People can speak not one language, but two languages (as a rule, they speak one better than the other). Bilingualism is usually caused by direct contacts between peoples, living together by people who speak different languages. Bilingualism can also occur without direct contacts between peoples, for example, when learning a language at school. Bilingual speakers - bilingual individuals - are called bilinguals. Bilingualism is usually understood as the knowledge of two languages and regular switching from one to another,

depending on the situation of communication. There are two questions here. The first is the definition of the difference between languages and the degree of this difference, the second is the degree of language proficiency. It is assumed that bilingualism occurs whenever a person switches from one language code to another in specific conditions of speech communication, regardless of whether it is a transition from one national language to another, or from a national language to a dialect. In this regard, the study of the situation of bilingualism acquires paramount importance. To what extent the language will change in the course of contacts, the direction and speed of changes, up to the disappearance of one of the languages, ultimately depends on socio-historical conditions. The problem of bilingualism contains a number of contentious issues. First of all, the very concept of bilingualism is controversial. Some foreign scientists understand bilingualism as not only the possession of two national or two ethnically and genetically homogeneous dialects or a literary language and a dialect belonging to one national language. It seems to us that with such an understanding, it is possible to reach the assertion that the possession of different styles of speech within the same national language is also bilingualism. It can be assumed that bilingualism exists not within the framework of one national language, but within the framework of two or more national languages.

The concept of bilingualism has several types:

-Subordinate bilingualism is bilingualism, in which there is a dominant language (language of thinking).

-Coordinative bilingualism is a bilingualism in which there is no dominant language. At the same time, Bilingual person thinks in the language in which he speaks.

The mechanism of bilingualism is the ability to easily move from one language to another. It is based on the formed switching skill. Switching skill - the ability to perform operations on the transition from one language to another to translate units of speech. Its functioning depends on the skills of speech hearing, probabilistic forecasting and self-control in the initial and translated languages.

In psycholinguistics, the acquisition and ownership of the priority of languages is differently denoted: L1-the first language or native and L2-the second language or acquired. The second language sometimes can subsequently supplant the first if it is dominant in this language environment. There are two types of bilingualism: natural (household) and artificial (educational).

Natural bilingualism occurs in the appropriate language environment, which includes radio and television with spontaneous speech practice. Awareness of the specifics of the language system may not occur. The second language in artificial

bilingualism is mastered in the educational environment, while the use of volitional efforts and special methods and techniques is necessary.

The analysis of the material shows that bilingualism is considered from various points of view and, therefore, is the subject of a number of related sciences.

Language is the main means of communication between people, and it is inseparable from man and human society. It is impossible to imagine a society in which there would be no language, and people would not communicate with each other. The language, reflecting the historical experience of society, serves as the means by which society spiritually forms an individual. From the first months of life, the child is exposed to adult speech, his tongue helps him create his first concepts, learn to operate on these concepts.

“Growing children with bilinguals is a very important solution. This affects their studies, social status, occupation, marital status and thinking. To be bilingual is more than to speak two languages. Bilingualism has educational, social, economic, cultural and political consequences.”

Two languages of a bilingual child are interdependent. Bilingualism is useful for children of any origin. When comparing children of bilinguals with children of monolinguals in different types of activities, the former always find themselves in a winning position.

“The bilingual child has a higher degree of mental development. They have a more original way of thinking and always several solutions to one problem. It is proved that a bilingual child is more capable and surpasses his peers in study. Bilingualism has no negative influence. It is very important that parents realize that the study of two languages requires a lot of time and effort, and the results appear at the beginning of the fourth grade. Bilingualism creates prospects for the development of cultural relations of people.”

The degree of development of speech inevitably affects the self-awareness of the child, when the ability to express his thoughts and understand the speech of others affects his place and role in society (the circle of friends and assessments at school, the opportunity to become a leader in a team, etc.). The level of use of the language depends on the variety, depth and correctness of the speech impressions that the child receives from early childhood. Therefore, it is so important to give the baby a full-fledged linguistic development at the age when the foundations of personality are formed, intelligence awakens.

The bilingualism has a positive effect on the development of memory, the ability to understand, analyze and discuss the phenomena of language, quick wits, and speed of reaction, mathematical skills and logic. Fully developing bilinguals, as a rule, learn well and better than others learn abstract sciences, literature and other foreign languages.

The younger the child, the more chances he has to master the second language in the maximum possible volume and with natural pronunciation. We can say unequivocally: children have an undeniable advantage in learning a foreign language over adults. The child's memory is more susceptible, unlike an adult, he is not constrained by complexes, is not afraid to make a mistake, not to remember the right word in time.

A bilingual child, unlike monolingual, is more interested in linguistic phenomena, since his language experience is much wider. Pretty to the semantics of words is manifested quite early, in the fact that the same concept can be expressed both in English and in Russian. This contributes to the development of translation skills, as well as interest in the motivation of names. With their own etymology of words, children actively use the knowledge of two languages.

Bilingualism develops spontaneously, if parents do not plan in advance the languages of communication with the child, mix them themselves, do not control the child's speech, and do not pay attention to its shortcomings. Sometimes spontaneous bilingualism develops if on the street children speak the language, other than at home, or "home" and "street" languages mix without any attention to such speech development from the parents. In the case of spontaneous development of bilingualism in the child's speech, too many mistakes arise.

Bilingualism has become one of the most striking phenomena of intercultural communication, defined as "communication of people representing different cultures". According to a number of researchers, there are more bilinguals in the world than monolinguals. It is known that to the present moment, children's bilingualism covers almost half of the children on our planet. It is believed that this trend will continue.

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